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Under pressure: accounting for multiple human pressures outside and inside marine protected areas in the Skagerrak

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The combined effects of multiple pressures pose critical threats to marine ecosystems. As an initial spatial assessment of cumulative pressures in the Skagerrak, we mapped where multiple pressures coincided with sensitive habitats and species, combining recent spatial data sets on 20 pressures and 39 habitats and species. The spatial data were linked with sensitivity weights obtained with a novel partly data-driven method. We found major spatial variation in the risk of cumulative impacts, identifying areas with high human impact, termed hot spots (such as shallow areas in southern and eastern Skagerrak), and areas with low human impact, termed cold spots (such as the deeper parts of the Norwegian Trench). The dominating human pressures were 1) fishing activities, 2) climate change, 3) underwater noise, 4) input of contaminants, 5) light pollution and 6) input of nutrients. Analyses of human pressures within and outside 20 Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) indicated significantly reduced levels in nine MPAs; however, these reductions were limited (less than 15%). One MPA (Skagens Gren og Skagerrak, DK) had significantly higher total human pressure inside the protected area, while ten MPAs did not yield significant results. We therefore recommend that the conservation measures in MPAs in the region be critically addressed and human pressures mitigated, to reduce the potential negative impact of human activities.

KEYWORDS

anthropogenic pressures, cumulative effect assessment (CEA), ecosystem-based management, fishing pressure, light pollution, marine biodiversity, sensitivity scores, underwater noise

1 Introduction

Marine waters, both coastal and offshore, are susceptible to anthropogenic pressures that impair species, habitats, and communities (Korpinen and Andersen, 2016; Halpern et al., 2008, 2025). The method for assessing cumulative human impact developed by Halpern et al. (2008) has served as a catalyst for numerous investigations conducted at national, regional, and international levels. Despite known shortcomings (e.g. Halpern and Fujita, 2013), it remains a widespread tool for analyzing where multiple pressures coincide with habitats and species that are sensitive to them (Korpinen and Andersen, 2016; Simeoni et al., 2023). Assessing the cumulative impact of multiple pressures on marine ecosystems is central to marine spatial planning (MSP) and ecosystem-based management and has been applied several times for the Baltic and North Sea (Andersen et al., 2013, 2023; Hammar et al., 2020; HELCOM, 2010; Jonsson et al., 2021; Korpinen et al., 2021).

The Skagerrak is a dynamic marginal sea connecting the Baltic and the North Sea and is characterized by complex hydrographic and geomorphological structure, including the deep Norwegian Trench, steep rocky coastlines along the Norwegian and Swedish coasts, and shallow sandy and muddy habitats in Danish coastal waters. This seascape diversity supports a rich and unique marine ecosystem with high species biodiversity and productivity (Buhl-Mortensen et al., 2023; Frigstad et al., 2023; Moland et al., 2025; Perry et al., 2018). Further, a recent meta-analysis showed complex and distinct population structures of several species and taxa within Skagerrak despite high connectivity with adjacent seas (Henriksson

et al., 2025). The ecosystem is under pressure from intensive bottom trawling (Eigaard et al., 2017), habitat degradation (Nikolaou et al., 2025), and climate change (Norderhaug et al., 2025). Stock assessments have documented declines in several commercially exploited species (ICES, 2022), and long-term biodiversity assessments suggest loss of rare deep-water and long-lived taxa (Obst et al., 2018), highlighting the need for improved management and protection. Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) in the region are largely limited to shallow (<200 m) coastal zones (Figure 1), while deep habitats found in the Norwegian Trench are largely unprotected, despite being nominated as ‘especially valuable area’ (SVO) due to the richness of ecosystem components meeting the criteria of Ecologically and Biologically Significant marine Areas (EBSA: Eriksen et al., 2021). In addition, the Norwegian Trench constitute an important carbon sink (Diesing et al., 2021, 2024).

To gain a more comprehensive understanding of risks related to combined effects of multiple pressures in the Skagerrak, we performed a Cumulative Effect Assessment (CEA) of multiple pressures on ecosystem components in the Skagerrak, asking: Where are the hotspot and cold spot areas regarding human impact in the Skagerrak? To answer this, we calculated a Human Impact Index (HII; Halpern et al., 2008), showing where multiple pressures coincided spatially with sensitive habitats and species, combining recent spatial data sets on 20 pressures and 39 habitats and species.

As a second step, we assessed the HII and the ranking of human pressures within and outside designated MPAs within the Skagerrak region to determine whether current management regulations reduce human pressures within the MPAs.

FIGURE 1

Map of the Skagerrak, showing its delimitation and boundaries as defined in this study, together with the location of designated Marine Protected Areas (MPAs). The figure also illustrates the division of Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs) between Norway, Sweden, and Denmark, with a darker shaded line indicating the coastal zone (i.e. one nautical mile (nm) outside the ‘baseline’). In the small map, the bathymetry of the area is illustrated.

2 Methods

The Skagerrak is a body of water bordered by Norway, Sweden and Denmark, situated between the North Sea and the Kattegat, with the latter being a transition zone between the greater North Sea region and the Baltic Sea (Figure 1). The western boundary of the Skagerrak, demarcating it from the North Sea, is defined by a line extending from Hanstholm, Denmark, to Lindesnes, Norway. The southern boundary, separating it from the Kattegat, is in this study delineated by a line connecting Grenen, Denmark, to Lerkil, Sweden, north of Marstrand (Figure 1). The Skagerrak has several nature protection areas, such as MPAs under the OSPAR agreement, the Natura 2000 network of MPAs, and marine national parks (Figure 1).

The circulation of the surface waters is on average cyclonic, and the Skagerrak is a melting pot of waters with different salinity and characteristics originating from the Atlantic and North Sea, Baltic Sea and local riverine input, creating the Norwegian Coastal Current flowing northwards along the Norwegian coast to the Barents Sea (Sætre, 2007).

The Norwegian Trench has depths down to 700 m in eastern Skagerrak and a deep sill in the west (approximately 280 m depth; Rodhe, 1996), providing a deep-sea habitat within Skagerrak with high rates of sediment accumulation and carbon deposition (Diesing et al., 2021, 2024).

2.1 Data sources

The starting point for establishing the Skagerrak-wide data set on pressures and human activities is the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive (Anon, 2008), which focuses on physical loss, physical damage, other physical disturbance, interference with hydrological processes, contamination by hazardous substances, release of other substances, nutrient and organic matter enrichment and biological disturbance. In this study, we also included climate change, noise and light and used a total of 12 themes and 20 individual pressures (detailed information about the data sets can be found in the [Supplementary Material 1](#)):

1. Climate change: A pressure group which in this study consist of four data layers (based on statistically downscaled CMIP6 ocean variables from Kristiansen et al., 2024) on changes in: 1) surface temperature, 2) bottom temperature, 3) surface pH, and 4) bottom pH. The changes were calculated as differences between the 30-year averages of 1993–2013 and 2015–2035 under scenario SSP 2-4.5. We used 30-year periods because climate pressures are conventionally assessed over multi-decadal averages to reduce short-term variability.
2. Fishing: Includes three different pressures for the period 2017–2024, based on Global Fishing Watch (GFW) data: 1) extraction of species by commercial fishing, 2) bycatch by pelagic towed gear, and 3) bycatch by bottom-touching mobile gear.
3. Noise: Maps of noise distribution include three data layers from different sources such as EMODnet and ICES: 1)

input of impulsive anthropogenic noise covering the period from 2014–2016, 2) input of continuous anthropogenic noise for 2017–2023 and 3) input of rumbling noise due to bottom trawling up to 2022.

4. Light: Includes two data layers: 1) artificial light at night (ALAN: Smyth et al., 2024) for 2019 and 2) coastal darkening (Davies and Smyth, 2025) from 2003 to 2022.
5. Disturbance due to general human presence and recreational activities: estimated disturbance based on CORINE artificial land cover and population along the coastline from 2018.
6. Non-indigenous species: Layer representing the count of non-indigenous species from 1989 to 2018 (Korpinen et al., 2021).
7. Changes in hydrological conditions from 2016 including physical alterations, dams, barriers, and hydrographical alterations reported under the Water Framework Directive (Korpinen et al., 2021).
8. Contaminants: input of hazardous substances in the area for 2013–2023, using the HELCOM Hazardous Substances Status Assessment Tool (CHASE) as a proxy for contaminant pressure (Andersen et al., 2016; EEA, 2019a).
9. Nutrients: input of nutrients in the area for 2013–2024, using the HELCOM Eutrophication Assessment Tool (HEAT) as a proxy for eutrophication pressure (EEA, 2019b).
10. Marine litter: The Marine Litter Assessment Tool (MALT) was used as a proxy for the accumulated litter pressure, which included seafloor litter, beach litter, and floating micro-litter for the period 2010–2021 (Murray et al., 2023).
11. Physical disturbance of the seafloor based on EMODnet Human Activities (EMODnet Human Activities, 2025) data from 2015 to 2024. It includes the following activities: anchoring, aquaculture (finfish and shellfish), cables, demersal fishing, dredging, dredge spoil dumping, offshore oil and gas installations, ports, sand and gravel extraction, offshore wind farms, and sediment resuspension from shipping.
12. Physical loss of the seabed based on EMODnet Human Activities (EMODnet Human Activities, 2025) data from 2015 to 2024. This was prepared similarly as Physical disturbance of the seafloor, but limited to: anchoring, aquaculture, cables, offshore oil and gas installations, dredge spoil dumping, sand and gravel extraction, offshore wind farms, and ports.

To correct for skewness and improve the representation of the spatial distribution of pressures, the data layers that had highly skewed distribution, such as fishing, noise and artificial light at night were (log+1)-transformed. Log transformation reduces the influence of extreme values and expands the mid-range, resulting in a more representative estimate of the area exposed to moderate and high pressure. Other layers were not transformed because their distributions were less skewed, and preserving their original scaling better reflected the variation in pressure intensity. As noted by Halpern and Fujita (2013), different transformations change how

skewed data and relative intensities appear, however they also state that there is no single optimal method. We therefore applied transformations only when they helped make pressures more comparable without altering their basic ecological pattern.

The inclusion of all ecologically relevant groups of organisms is a prerequisite for ecosystem-based Cumulative Effect Assessment (CEA). Hence, this study focuses on a broad range of organisms, ranging from primary producers (both pelagic and species-specific benthic habitats), over a broad range of benthic habitats to top predators such as seals and harbor porpoise. Our data consist of six groups comprising 39 individual ecosystem components (detailed information about the data sets can be found in the [Supplementary Material 2](#)):

1. Pelagic habitats: Chlorophyll-a in surface waters was used as a representation of the planktonic community. Since phytoplankton is naturally present throughout the study area and chlorophyll-a levels show substantial natural variability unrelated to human impact, this layer was not used quantitatively. Instead, it was set to a value of 1 to reflect that the pelagic habitats are omnipresent across the region. Oxygen depletion was not included, as hypoxic conditions ($<4 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) were not observed within the study area.
2. Broad-scale benthic habitats: Obtained from EMODnet, collected for the period 2019 to 2023, including infralittoral 1) coarse sediments, 2) sand and muddy sand, 3) mud, 4) mixed sediments, 5) rocks and biogenic reefs; circalittoral 6) coarse sediments, 7) sand and muddy sand, 8) mud, 9) mixed sediments, 10) rocks and biogenic reefs; offshore circalittoral 11) coarse sediments, 12) sand and muddy sand, 13) o mud, 14) mixed sediments, 15) rocks and biogenic reefs, and 16) bathyal seabed.
3. Species-specific benthic habitats: This group consists of three data layers: 1) UNEP Eelgrass *Zostera marina* distribution up to 2021, 2) UNEP Cold-water corals presence data up to 2021 and 3) Modelled kelp distribution for 1) tangle kelp (*Laminaria hyperborea*) and 2) sugar kelp (*Saccharina latissima*), based on observational data from 2001 to 2018, depending on the location (Kvile et al., 2022).
4. Seabirds: Modelled distribution based on observational data from 1980 to 2011 from ICES ESAS for the following species: 1) auks, *Alcidae*, 2) common scoter, *Melanitta nigra*, 3) divers, *Gavia* spp., 4) eider duck, *Somateria mollissima*, 5) fulmar, *Fulmar* spp., 6) long-tailed duck, *Clangula hyemalis*, and 7) red-breasted merganser, *Mergus serrator*.
5. Marine mammals: 1) categorical distribution based on a 30-year mean up to 2023 of harbor seal, *Phoca vitulina*; 2) SCANS-III predicted density based on data from 1994 to 2016 of the common minke whale, *Balaenoptera acutorostrata*; and 4) SCANS-III predicted density based on data from 1994 to 2016 of harbor porpoise, *Phocoena phocoena*.

6. Fish: Maps on the relative abundance of fish species originating from the SAMSKAG project dataset (Moland et al., 2025), including the following species: 1) anglerfish, *Lophius piscatorius*, 2) Atlantic cod, *Gadus morhua*, 3) Atlantic halibut, *Hippoglossus hippoglossus*, 4) Atlantic herring, *Clupea harengus*, 5) Atlantic wolffish, *Anarhichas lupus*, 6) Common sole, *Solea solea*, 7) European hake, *Merluccius merluccius*, 8) European plaice, *Pleuronectes platessa*, 9) greater forkbeard, *Phycis blennoides*, 10) haddock, *Melanogrammus aeglefinus*, 11) ling, *Molva molva*, 12) Norway pout, *Trisopterus esmarkii*, 13) rabbitfish, *Chimaera monstrosa* and 14) saithe, *Pollachius virens*.

To correct for skewness and improve the representation of the spatial distribution of abundance, the data layers for fish were (log +1)-transformed (see notes on transformation of data layers for pressures above).

2.2 Sensitivity scores

The Spatial Cumulative Assessment of Impact Risk for Management tool (SCAIRM; Piet et al., 2023) is a method that seeks to integrate multiple pieces of information on population dynamics into risk assessments. The method is broadly composed of two components; 1) 'Exposure', describing the spatial overlap between pressures and ecosystem component, and 2) 'Effect Potential', that incorporates resilience, behaviour, frequency of interactions, and hazard potential to account for population dynamics when estimating the sensitivity of ecosystem components to pressures. The incorporation of such parameters remains expert opinion-based but is performed through transparent and verifiable classification schemes for each parameter (see below), which are then used to calculate the overall effect potential. This realigns sensitivity score estimations which better reflect the relationship between the ecosystem components and pressures (see Halpern et al., 2007). Therefore, SCAIRM provides a structured platform for scoring the sensitivity of an ecosystem component to a pressure. This method differs from the traditional expert-based sensitivity score (cf., Kallio et al., 2025), often used in CEA assessments, where the sensitivity of an ecosystem component to a pressure is based on a rough evaluation of the effect of the pressure on a numeric scale e.g. ranging from 0 to 4. Given the more structured sensitivity assessment in the SCAIRM 'Effect Potential' component, we opted to replace the traditional expert-based sensitivity scores with SCARIM-based sensitivity scores. A conceptual figure and more information on the calculation of sensitivity scores can be found in the [Supplementary Material 3](#).

To estimate sensitivity scores, we followed the procedures of the SCAIRM method as described in Piet et al. (2023), but with some simple modifications to allow for its incorporation into the spatial Human Impact Index (HII) calculations. First, the estimation of ecosystem components' exposure to pressures in SCAIRM is based on expert-based estimation while the HII uses spatial data layers that more precisely determine exposure. Therefore, we removed the

'Exposure' section of SCAIRM and only used the 'Effect Potential' section as estimation of sensitivity. The next step was to calculate 'Effect Potential' for each combination of ecosystem components and pressure, using resilience, hazard, behaviour, magnitude, and frequency, following the methodology described by Piet et al. (2023). Supplementary Material 3 contains tables with exact criteria for scoring each of these parameters. In brief, resilience was evaluated as the number of years that the ecosystem component would take to recover, given that pressure was removed. Hazard was defined as the depletion of an ecosystem component from a single exposure to the pressure. Here nuances can be made regarding whether scoring hazard at population level or individual level. We took a pragmatic approach by considering how the pressure is likely to affect the ecosystem component and what the overall hazard can be. For example, fishing will presumably not decimate a whole population of herring, nor does it only kill one individual, but for the number of herring caught the pressure is lethal. Therefore, the hazard of fishing on herring was ranked 'lethal high' (likely causing serious and irreversible harm), that is the maximum score. On the other hand, the hazard of the pressure 'Disturbance of species (breeding, resting, feeding) due to human presence' on birds was ranked 'lethal low', suggesting that it is potentially unsustainable at high recovery potential. This pressure is not directly lethal; however, displacement of habitat and breeding/feeding grounds can be unsustainable for the population exposed if the pressure does not cease. Behaviour was scored based on the likelihood of interaction between the ecosystem component and the pressure, thus capturing whether the ecosystem component can or cannot avoid the pressure, and whether it is attracted to it or not (Supplementary Material 3). Frequency was scored as the expected number of interactions between a pressure and an ecosystem component in an average year. Finally, magnitude is defined as the average strength of the pressure in the area of exposure to the ecosystem component. Given the area of our assessment (with large spatial variation in pressure strength), we set all magnitude levels in the calculations to 1 before calculating the final effect potential (sensitivity score). This meant that magnitude does not impact our sensitivity calculations, since this effect is captured in data layers on pressures and ecosystem components, hence ensuring that we did not duplicate the magnitude estimation in the HII analysis.

Based on the classification of the different parameters above, we calculated the effect potential for each combination of pressure and ecosystem component by first calculating resistance, recovery rate, and depletion rate using the equations from Piet et al. (2023):

$$\text{Effect Potential} = R_d / (R_r + R_d).$$

where R_d is the depletion rate per year defined by $\ln(1/\text{resistance})$, and R_r is the recovery rate per year defined by $\ln(50)/\text{resilience}$. Resistance is defined as:

$$\text{Resistance} = (1 - H * B * M)^F.$$

where H = hazard, B = Behaviour, M = Magnitude, and F = Frequency (for continuous frequency, F is removed from the equation) as described above.

Values for effect potential were scaled between 0 to 1, where 0 represents no sensitivity and 1 represents maximum sensitivity. Our sensitivity scores represent the estimated impact of the pressure when the ecosystem component is fully exposed to the pressure. All

the estimated and calculated parameters, along with the final sensitivity scores, are included in SM3.

2.3 Calculations

We calculated the Human Impact Index (HII) using an established model that quantifies the spatial overlap between pressures and sensitive ecosystem components (Figure 2). Despite its known limitations (Halpern and Fujita, 2013), it has been widely used in marine spatial planning and ecosystem assessments because of its transparency and reproducibility (Korpinen and Andersen, 2016). We used the version of the model implemented in the EcoImpactMapper software (Stock, 2016), with the adjustments described below.

The model is based on three types of spatial input data: 1) Intensity of human pressure (D_i), such as marine litter, 2) Distribution of key ecosystem components (e_j), for example, fish species; and 3) Sensitivity scores ($\mu_{i,j}$), which describe the sensitivity of ecosystem component j to stressor i .

All the spatial datasets were represented in a regular 1×1 km grid. To ensure comparability among layers expressed in different units (e.g. probability of presence, concentration, or density), both pressure and ecosystem component data were scaled to a maximum value of 1.

For each grid cell (x, y), the combined effect of each pressure on each ecosystem component was calculated. The mean impact across all pressure–ecosystem component combinations was then computed to derive the Human Impact Index (I_{mean}), thereby avoiding the conflation of high-intensity pressures with the number of ecosystem components in a cell (Equation 1). This approach has been increasingly adopted in recent studies (Andersen et al., 2020a, 2020b, 2023; Halpern et al., 2015). To ensure equal representation of the key ecosystem component groups, the HII was first calculated separately for each group and then summed to obtain the integrated HII. The index is calculated as follows:

$$I_{\text{mean}} = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m \left(\frac{1}{E_{\text{Div}(x,y)}} \right) D_i(x, y) e_j(x, y) \mu_{i,j} \quad (1)$$

where

$$E_{\text{Div}(x,y)} = \sum_{j=1}^m e_j(x, y) \quad (2)$$

In addition to the impact index, the relative contributions of each pressure group and ecosystem group to the total index were quantified. The spatial distributions of the ecosystem components and pressures were further summarized by computing an ecosystem index (Equation 2) and an unweighted stressor index, following Stock (2016).

The robustness of the impact index was assessed using 1,000 Monte Carlo simulations (Stock et al., 2018). In this context, robustness refers to the stability of the calculated impact values under the sources of uncertainty included in the simulations. Each simulation incorporated alternative ecologically acceptable model assumptions and random variations in the input data to account for uncertainty (i.e.: spatial resolution, sensitivity score errors, etc.).

Areas consistently appearing among the top 25% of impact values across at least 90% of the simulation runs, were classified as robust high-impact areas (hotspots). Conversely, areas consistently falling within the lowest 25% of impact values across at least 90% simulated runs were classified as robust low-impact areas (cold spots).

Finally, we compared the total pressure (calculated by summing pressure values) inside and outside marine protected areas (MPAs). MPA boundaries were obtained from official national spatial data and Natura2000 datasets following the procedure from Moland et al., 2025. When extracting pressure values from the cumulative stressor index map (EcoImpactMapper), grid cells intersecting an MPA boundary were excluded, as their values cannot be assigned clearly to either side. Overlapping or adjacent MPAs were merged into a single larger and external conditions were characterized using a 5-km buffer around each MPA, excluding areas overlapping other MPAs. Differences between the inside and outside pressures of the MPAs were assessed using a linear model (Equation 3).

$$value_{ijk} = \mu + \beta Type_i + \gamma MPA_j + \delta (Type \cdot MPA)_{ij} + \epsilon_{ijk} \quad (3)$$

where μ is the overall mean, $Type(i)$ indicates whether a given cell is inside (1) or outside (2) an MPA area, β is the estimated change in values when going from type 1 to type 2, $MPA(j)$ indicates which area the cell belongs to, γ represents the MPA-specific effect, the interaction term (δ) allows the areas to increase or decrease at different magnitudes, and ϵ is the error term. The three variables (Type, MPA, and their interaction term) were significant on an overall level. In order to identify which areas were significant, the marginal means (least squared means) were estimated using the emmeans package in R. Additionally, pairwise comparisons between the two area types were conducted for each MPA, applying Tukey's *post-hoc* correction to control the family-wise error rate and reduce the risk of Type I errors arising from multiple

testing. The magnitude of these differences is expressed as the percentage change between the mean inside and outside pressures for each MPA relative to the mean outside pressure. If the MPA had fewer than 10 cells within the boundaries, it was determined to be too small for assessment. The list of MPAs included in the analyses and plots showing results using the impact index (instead of summed pressures) are given in the Supplementary Material 4.

3 Results

Mapping of cumulative effects provides a simple and effective visualization of which areas are most affected by human activities, and where they overlap with sensitive species or habitats with high biodiversity or other qualities of management concern. Higher values of the Human Impact Index (HII, Figure 3) indicate that several pressures occur simultaneously, they have high intensity, and/or the ecosystem components present are sensitive to these pressures. Therefore, a high HII indicates a high risk of negative human impact on the marine ecosystem. This study included 20 data layers for human pressure and 39 data layers for ecosystem components.

As stated, a novel methodological aspect of this study is replacing the traditional expert-based sensitivity scores with a structured and partially data-driven approach based on SCAIRM (Piet et al., 2023). The magnitude of pressure and exposure are given by the data layers, while resilience and resistance were categorized following the SCAIRM approach to obtain the overall sensitivity scores (Figure 4). Overall, the species-specific benthic habitats, pelagic habitats, marine mammals, and fish had the highest sensitivities to a wide range of pressures, while the broad-scale

FIGURE 3 Human impact index (HII) showing the estimated cumulative effects of human pressures in the Skagerrak. White isolines illustrate the bathymetry of the region.

benthic habitats were mostly sensitive to physical disturbance/loss of the seabed.

Wide areas of the Skagerrak were affected by human impacts (Figure 3), with more than half of the study region having moderate to high HII. The human impact is generally highest in regions shallower than 300–400 meters, resulting in a wide band of high human impact along the relatively shallow Danish and Swedish coasts, and a narrow band along the steeper Norwegian coast. The

Norwegian Trench (deeper than 500 m) is clearly visible in Figure 3, with a relatively low human impact.

We identified areas of high human impact (hotspots) and low human impact (cold spots) that were robust to model assumptions and input data quality with Monte Carlo simulations (Figure 5). Robust hotspots occurred in relatively shallow areas in southern and eastern Skagerrak (mostly within the Swedish and Danish EEZ) and in a narrow band slightly offshore along the Norwegian coast.

FIGURE 4 An overview of the sensitivity scores (normalized between 0-1), see Section 2.2, for calculations. The y-axis shows pressures, and the x-axis shows ecosystem components. More information on sensitivity scores and individual values can be found in Supplementary Material 3.

FIGURE 5 Robust hotspots and cold spots are defined as areas consistently exhibiting the 25% highest or lowest, respectively, impact index values in at least 90% of the Monte Carlo simulations (see calculations in Section 2.3).

These regions have many pressures and high levels of fishing, underwater noise, inputs of contaminants and nutrients, and physical disturbance to the seabed. Large robust cold spots occurred only in the central and eastern Norwegian Trench, where fishing pressure and associated pressures from rumbling noise (bottom trawling) and physical disturbances to the seabed were low. There were also small robust cold spots in Jammerbugt, off the Danish coast.

The six human pressures that contributed most to the HII in the Skagerrak were fishing, climate, underwater noise, light and inputs of nutrients and contaminants (Figure 6). The ecosystem components under the most pressure were fish, marine mammals, pelagic habitat, and broad-scale benthic habitats. Species extraction by fishing (including target species and bycatch) alone accounted for approximately half of the HII (Figure 6), whereas fishing also contributed to underwater noise (through continuous sound and rumbling noise due to trawling) and physical disturbance to the seafloor (through bottom trawling).

Climate contributed roughly 10% to the HII (Figure 6), representing the pressure arising from recent changes (absolute difference between the average of the periods 1993–2013 and 2015–2035) in surface and bottom temperatures and pH.

Fishing and climate change are widespread in the Skagerrak, and there is a high sensitivity of many ecosystem components to these pressures. Although the inputs of nutrients and contaminants have smaller spatial extents, they affect large areas of the eastern Skagerrak and coastal regions. For inputs of contaminants and nutrients, we used status assessments of Contamination Ratios and Eutrophication Ratios, respectively, as a proxy for these two pressures where the status of ‘Good’ or above corresponds to zero pressure, while ‘Good’ or worse status corresponds proportionally to a pressure intensity from 0 to 1 (See SM1). Generally, there are areas below ‘Good’ eutrophication status in the eastern half of the Skagerrak, and along coastal regions for all three nations.

Across the 20 Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) analyzed, the total human pressure (calculated by summing pressure values) was

FIGURE 6 Sankey diagram showing the relations between pressures (left bar) and ecosystem components (right bar). The width of the bands is relative to the Human Impact Index (HII), and each color indicates a specific pressure.

FIGURE 7

For the map of the MPAs included in the assessment, please note that overlapping and adjacent MPAs were merged for the analyses. The color code indicates whether the sum of pressures inside the MPAs was larger or lower than the buffer zone surrounding the MPA (5 km). The asterisk (*) indicates MPAs smaller than ten 1 km² grid cells, and the results should be interpreted with caution. MPA names in bold indicate significance (p-value < 0.05).

TABLE 1 Analyses of pressures inside and outside the MPAs.

Area	Country	Inside ± SD	Outside ± SD	Category	P-value	Dominating pressure groups
MPA1	Denmark	5.55 ± 0.42	6.43 ± 0.49	5-15% lower	<.0001	1) Fishing, 2) Noise, 3) Light, 4) Physical loss of seabed
MPA2	Denmark	6.4 ± 0.41	7.02 ± 0.41	5-15% lower	<.0001	1) Fishing, 2) Contaminants, 3) Climate, 4) Nutrients
MPA3	Denmark	5.93 ± 0.32	5.84 ± 0.59	0-5% higher	0.518	1) Fishing, 2) Noise, 3) Climate, 4) Nutrients
MPA4*	Denmark	7.54	7.48 ± 0.84	0-5% higher	0.948	1) Fishing, 2) Noise, 3) Contaminants, 4) Nutrients
MPA5	Denmark	8.72 ± 0.78	8.27 ± 0.66	5-15% higher	<.0001	1) Fishing, 2) Noise, 3) Climate, 4) Light
MPA6	Norway	5.4 ± 0.82	5.29 ± 1.11	0-5% higher	0.092	1) Fishing, 2) Climate, 3) Nutrients, 4) Light
MPA7	Norway	4.94 ± 0.29	5.88 ± 0.86	>15% lower	<.0001	1) Contaminants, 2) Climate, 3) Light, 4) Noise
MPA8	Norway	6.07 ± 0.87	6.59 ± 1.31	5-15% lower	<.0001	1) Fishing, 2) Climate, 3) Contaminants, 4) Nutrients
MPA9*	Norway	4.67	5.43 ± 0.41	5-15% lower	0.455	1) Fishing, 2) Nutrients, 3) Noise, 4) Light
MPA10	Norway	6.35 ± 1.07	7.38 ± 1.55	5-15% lower	<.0001	1) Fishing, 2) Contaminants, 3) Noise, 4) Nutrients
MPA11	Sweden	7.66 ± 1.69	8.1 ± 1.11	5-15% lower	<.0001	1) Fishing, 2) Contaminants, 3) Noise, 4) Nutrients
MPA12	Sweden	6.61 ± 1.3	6.92 ± 1.39	0-5% lower	<.0001	1) Fishing, 2) Nutrients, 3) Light, 4) Noise
MPA13	Sweden	7.54 ± 0.9	7.53 ± 0.92	0-5% higher	0.954	1) Fishing, 2) Noise, 3) Nutrients, 4) Climate
MPA14*	Sweden	6.96	7.57 ± 0.56	5-15% lower	0.561	1) Fishing, 2) Noise, 3) Nutrients, 4) Climate
MPA15*	Sweden	6.76 ± 0.24	6.7 ± 0.63	0-5% higher	0.901	1) Fishing, 2) Nutrients, 3) Climate, 4) Noise
MPA16*	Sweden	5.68 ± 0.23	7.11 ± 0.41	>15% lower	0.053	1) Nutrients, 2) Climate, 3) Noise, 4) Light
MPA17*	Sweden	6.05	7.13 ± 0.57	>15% lower	0.307	1) Nutrients, 2) Noise, 3) Climate, 4) Light
MPA18*	Sweden	6.13 ± 0.08	7.05 ± 0.85	5-15% lower	0.120	1) Nutrients, 2) Fishing, 3) Noise, 4) Climate
MPA19	Sweden	6.4 ± 0.45	7.05 ± 1.26	5-15% lower	0.026	1) Fishing, 2) Noise, 3) Climate, 4) Contaminants
MPA20	Sweden	6.9 ± 0.4	7.77 ± 1.23	5-15% lower	<.0001	1) Nutrients, 2) Noise, 3) Climate, 4) Light

For the names of the individual MPAs included, see [Supplementary Material 4](#), while the location of the different MPAs is shown in [Figure 7](#). SD, standard deviation; *too small to be assessed; names in bold, significant (p-value < 0.05).

generally lower inside MPAs than in their surrounding 5 km buffer zone (Figure 7, Table 1; see the names of MPAs in SM4). Of the 20 MPAs, nine areas showed significantly lower total pressure within the protected area, where most showed small (5–15%) differences, whereas MPA 7 (Jomfruland nasjonalpark) showed more than 15% reduction within the protected area. There was one MPA with a significantly higher total pressure within the protected area relative to the buffer zone, MPA 5 (Skagens Gren and Skagerrak, see Table 1) in Denmark with 5–15% higher pressure within the protected area. All three nations (Norway, Sweden and Denmark) had MPAs that showed no significant change (ten MPAs in total), either due to no actual change in pressure levels or too few samples (grid cells within MPA) to identify a change in pressure. Generally, MPAs including offshore waters (MPA 5, 6, 12) had higher total pressure than nearshore MPAs.

Fishing was the dominant stressor group across nearly all MPAs, followed by underwater noise, nutrient input, and climate-related pressures. In some cases, the input of contaminants and light pollution also substantially contributed to the overall pressure levels (see Table 1).

4 Discussion

This is the first study to perform a detailed CEA for the whole Skagerrak Basin, including the Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) of Norway, Sweden and Denmark, in addition to including novel drivers such as rumbling noise from trawling and light pollution. However, the spatial variations and level of human impact correspond to studies on the European scale (Korpinen et al., 2021) and Norwegian, Danish and Swedish coastal regions (Aarflot et al., 2024; Andersen et al., 2023; Hammar et al., 2020).

Sensitivity scores for CEA are normally obtained through expert surveys or workshops (e.g., Halpern et al., 2007; Doubleday et al., 2017). Averaged across many experts, such scores qualitatively agree on which pressures are most important for specific ecosystem components, but individual experts' scores often disagree profoundly (Kallio et al., 2025). Hence, more disciplined and theory-grounded methods to set these scores are needed. In this study, we accordingly employed a more structured approach following the SCAIRM methodology, which represents, to our knowledge, the first time this approach has been applied. While elements of subjectivity remain, we consider this application a major improvement over the prior *ad-hoc* methods for setting sensitivity scores.

The human impact index (HII) shows that several human pressures overlap in space with the distribution of many key species and habitats, with many of the habitats having important function and high biodiversity. High HII values therefore indicate a high risk for negative combined effects. The human footprint on the Skagerrak is large, with more than half of the region having a moderate to high human impact index. Hotspots for human impact were identified in the southern and eastern Skagerrak and offshore along the Norwegian coast.

The dominant pressure in the Skagerrak region was fishing, including within most of the MPAs in the region (Table 1). Fishing

includes extraction of target species and pelagic and benthic bycatch, in addition fishing activities also contribute to other human pressures, such as noise (through continuous sound and rumbling noise due to bottom trawling) and physical disturbances to the seafloor (through bottom trawling). This result mirrors the findings of Hammar et al. (2020) where fishing was found dominant among human pressure along the Swedish west coast. The Skagerrak is among the most intensively trawled regions in the world (Eigaard et al., 2017; Pitcher et al., 2022). The trawling intensity in the Skagerrak is highest along the southern edge of the Norwegian trench at depths between 50–200 meters (where a single area can be trawled more than 10 times per year), while the trawling intensity is lower between 200–500 meters (trawled from two to five times per year), and mostly non-existent below 500 meters (Eigaard et al., 2017). This corresponds to the steep gradient in HII around this depth gradient (between 300–400m, Figure 3), and the reduced pressure intensity below these depths in the Norwegian Trench. However, the nearshore fishing activities could be underestimated, because the fishing pressure data layers used (Global Fishing Watch) underestimates fishing from vessels smaller than 12 to 15 m, which until recently were not required to use VMS tracking. Fishing activities naturally have the largest impact on fish populations (represented by the fish richness distribution of 14 species; see SM2), which were also the most impacted ecosystem component (Figure 6). However, there were also impacts from fishing on marine mammals and seabirds (through bycatch), and broad-scale benthic habitats impacted by mobile bottom-contacting gear (e.g. through bottom trawling for shrimp and the mixed species bottom trawl fishery targeting Norway lobster (*Nephrops norvegicus*)).

The climate pressure in this study reflects the impact of the changes between recent (1993–2013) and short-term future (2015–2035) temperature and pH and is the second most important human pressure in the Skagerrak region. In Halpern et al. (2025), cumulative impacts were found to double by mid-century, with the largest contributions coming from ocean warming (both surface and benthic) and biomass loss due to fisheries. A study from the Baltic and Kattegat (Wahlström et al., 2022), found that by the end of the century the impact of projected climate change alone will be of the same magnitude as all current pressures on the marine environment.

The contribution of underwater noise was the third most important pressure for the Skagerrak and represents input of impulsive (pulse-block-days) and continuous (vessel density/shipping) sound, in addition to rumbling noise from bottom trawling. Underwater sound from human activities such as shipping, industrial operations or bottom trawling can have negative effects on the marine ecosystem (Basan et al., 2024), especially for fish and marine mammals that use sound for various purposes (such as navigation and/or communication; Erbe et al., 2019; De Robertis and Handegard, 2013). In this study, both fish and marine mammals had sensitivities to noise pressure, however the largest impact were found for marine mammals.

The contributions of inputs of contaminants and nutrients to the HII were of similar magnitude, ranked fourth and sixth, respectively. By design, the spatial extent of a pressure will determine the contribution of the pressure to the HII. Therefore,

pressures with a smaller spatial extent will have a smaller contribution to the HII, regardless of the number of species and habitats that have a high sensitivity to this pressure. There were areas with lower status than ‘Good’ for contaminants and eutrophication in eastern and southern Skagerrak, and in the coastal waters of all three nations. Historically, eutrophication has been a major concern in Skagerrak, however, there has been an overall reduction in nutrient levels in many coastal regions due to management efforts to reduce nutrient loading over the past decades (Carstensen et al., 2006; Frigstad et al., 2023; Ramon et al., 2025). Nevertheless, ecosystem recovery from eutrophication has failed to manifest in many coastal regions, due to climate change, changes in ecosystem structure and function and synergistic effects with other human pressures (Frigstad et al., 2023; Duarte et al., 2009).

Light pollution is a novel human pressure to include in CEA, even though Artificial Light at Night (ALAN) was included as a human pressure in Halpern et al., 2025. In this study, light pollution (both ALAN and coastal darkening) was ranked fifth of the human pressures. The Skagerrak is among the hotspot regions globally for both ALAN (Smyth et al., 2024) and coastal darkening (Davies and Smyth, 2025). Coastal darkening reduces the light availability in the water column and therefore has potentially strong impacts on ecosystem productivity and food web structure, yet with different drivers than ALAN. In brief, increased inputs of terrestrially derived dissolved organic matter (DOM) has occurred in the Skagerrak catchment over the past decades, affecting light attenuation, and thereby causing coastal darkening (Opdal et al., 2023). This can have negative effects not only on euphotic depth and primary producers such as phytoplankton and macroalgae (Frigstad et al., 2023; Opdal et al., 2019), but also visual predators like fish, while potentially benefitting non-visual feeders like jellyfish (Aksnes et al., 2009).

Large cold spots occurred only in the central and eastern Norwegian trench, where fishing pressure and associated pressures from rumbling noise (bottom trawling) and physical disturbances to the seabed were low. The Norwegian Trench thereby represent the only region in the Skagerrak with relatively low human impact and could therefore be a candidate for a new protected area in the region, as also suggested by Moland et al., 2025. This deep-sea region is recognized for high carbon storage (Diesing et al., 2021, 2024), with potential for increased storage capacity if left undisturbed by bottom-trawling (Porz et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2024), high biodiversity and potential refugia for rare and cold-water species (Obst et al., 2018; Eriksen et al., 2021).

Of the 20 MPA regions assessed, only nine were found to have significantly reduced human pressure within the MPA relative to the surrounding area, and most of these were relatively small reductions (0–5 and 5–15% reduction categories). Six MPAs were found to have higher total pressure within the protected area, although the difference was significant only for MPA 5 (Skagens gren og Skagerrak). The most frequent dominant pressure within the MPAs were fishing activities, which can seem surprising, but commercial bottom trawling is frequent within MPAs and can even be higher than in unprotected areas (Dureuil et al., 2018). The need to increase protection measures within MPAs is highlighted across

many studies (Dureuil et al., 2018; Roessger et al., 2022; Stephenson et al., 2025), without which there is limited prospects of achieving the desired conservation outcomes of designated MPAs. Especially strictly protected areas or so-called ‘no-take marine reserves’, where extractive activities are prohibited, have been shown to yield increased conservation outcomes (Sala and Giakoumi, 2018). Recently, the Norwegian Government enforced no-fishing zones partially overlapping with the two MPAs in the outer Oslofjord (Færder and Ytre Hvaler nasjonalpark) and in the inner Oslofjord for the next 10 years (Regjeringen, 2025), which if sustained gives hope for measurable decreased human impact and positive ecosystem effects being observed for the coming decades.

5 Conclusions and outlook

The Skagerrak is subject to multiple human activities and pressures. In this study, we included all available ecologically relevant pressures and mapped their potential combined effects on marine ecosystems, ranging from pelagic habitats over benthic habitat to fish, seabirds, and marine mammals.

Based on our mapping of combined effects (2013–2024), we ranked the pressures and ecosystem components. The dominant pressures in the Skagerrak are 1) fishing, 2) climate, 4) underwater noise, 4) input of contaminants, 5) light pollution, and 6) inputs of nutrients. The most affected ecosystem components are 1) Fish, 2) Marine mammals, 3) Pelagic habitats and 4) Broad-scale benthic habitats.

The human impact in the Skagerrak shows large spatial variations, however over half of the region have moderate to high human impact index (HII). Hotspots of human impact are found in the relatively shallow eastern and southern North Sea, within the Swedish and Danish EEZ. In addition, a narrow band was observed slightly offshore along the Norwegian coast. Large cold spot areas were only found in the central and eastern Norwegian Trench, where fishing and associated pressures from noise and physical disturbance was low.

Providing an answer to whether current management regulations reduce human pressures is MPA-specific. Across the 20 MPAs, nine had significantly reduced human pressures within the protected area, though most of these had limited reductions (less than 15%). One MPA (Skagens Gren og Skagerrak, DK) had significantly higher total human pressure inside the protected area. Ten MPAs did not yield significant results. We therefore recommend that the conservation measures within MPAs in the Skagerrak be critically addressed, and that human pressures within protected areas needs to be increasingly mitigated.

Data availability statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article/Supplementary Material. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

Author contributions

HF: Conceptualization, Investigation, Project administration, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. JHA: Conceptualization, Investigation, Project administration, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. TB: Investigation, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. LH: Investigation, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. AH: Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. DH: Investigation, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. TM: Formal analysis, Investigation, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. EM: Investigation, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. CM: Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. HS: Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. AS: Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. JMA: Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. PR: Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

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Supplementary material

The Supplementary Material for this article can be found online at: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fmars.2026.1774106/full#supplementary-material>

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